

Synthesis of some New Pyrido[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine Derivatives and their Antibacterial Activity

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In an earlier publication we reported the synthesis of cyanopyridines¹. Our interest in pyrido[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines² prompted us to synthesise some new 4-imino-3,5,7-trisubstituted-pyrido[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine-2(1*H*)-thiones (2) by the condensation of cyanopyridines (1) with arylisothiocyanates (Scheme 1). These compounds (2a-j) were characterised by elemental analysis, ir and nmr spectral studies, and screened for antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* by paper disc method³. All the compounds exhibited significant activity against *S. aureus* (zone of inhibition, 7-14 mm), but no activity against *E. coli*.

Experimental

The cyanopyridines (1) were synthesised according to the reported method¹: 2-amino-3-cyano-

Scheme 1

4-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-6-phenylpyridine (1a; 38%), m.p. 170-72°; 2-amino-3-cyano-4-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-6-phenylpyridine (1b; 36%), m.p. 165°.

4-Imino-3,5,7-trisubstituted-pyrido[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine-2(1*H*)-thiones (2): A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol), aryl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol), dioxane (15 ml) and pyridine (2 ml) was heated at 150° for about 22 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and poured into crushed ice. The resulting solid was washed with water, dried and recrystallised from DMF-ethanol (1 : 2) or from glacial acetic acid (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2*

Compd. no	R ¹	R ²	R ³	Molecular formula	M p. °C	Yield %
2a	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -Cl C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ ClN ₄ OS	265	70
2b	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -Cl C ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -OC ₂ H ₅ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ ClN ₄ OS	220	61
2c	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -Cl C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -Br C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₁₆ BrClN ₄ S	322	69
2d	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -Cl C ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -F.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₅ H ₁₆ FCIN ₄ S	289	68
2e	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -F.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₅ H ₁₆ FCIN ₄ S	326	69
2f	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	185	70
2g	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -OC ₂ H ₅ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	210	69
2h	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -Br.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₁₆ BrN ₄ OS	220	65
2i	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -F.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₁₆ FN ₄ OS	248	68
2j	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ OS	282	71

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

TABLE 2—Ir AND Nmr SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2

Compd no.	ν _{max} (cm ⁻¹)				δ				
	NH	C=NH	C=S	NH-C=S	NH	C=NH	ArH	OCH ₃	OCH ₂ CH ₃
2a	3 380	3 110	1 190	1 440, 1 480, 1 555	8.81	-9.08(d)	6 70-8.34(m)	—	1.44 (t) 4.12(q) 1.44(t)
2b	3 360	3 120	1 195	1 445, 1 485, 1 560	8.80	-9.06(d)	6.73-8.30(m)	—	1.44(t) 4.12(q)
2c	3 350	3 120	1 190	1 435, 1 470, 1 550	8.20	-8.47(d)	6.59-7.70(m)	—	—
2d	3 360	3 120	1 195	1 450, 1 485, 1 560	8.27	-8.54(d)	6.73-8.07(m)	—	—
2e	3 350	3 110	1 190	1 435, 1 475, 1 560	7.90	-8.17(d)	6.50-7.77(m)	—	—
2f	3 360	3 120	1 190	1 440, 1 490, 1 560	8.20	-8.47(d)	6.50-7.70(m)	3.82(s)	1.40(t) 4.15(q)
2g	3 340	3 110	1 195	1 430, 1 485, 1 550	7.83	-8.24(d)	6.70-7.77(m)	3.82(s)	1.40(t) 4.15(q)
2h	3 370	3 120	1 190	1 440, 1 490, 1 555	7.96	-8.37(d)	6.70-7.90(m)	3.82(s)	—
2i	3 370	3 120	1 185	1 450, 1 500, 1 560	8.27	-8.81(d)	7.13-8.26(m)	3.84(s)	—
2j	3 350	3 120	1 190	1 430, 1 495, 1 585	7.94	-8.52(d)	6.95-7.89(m)	3.86(s)	—

Melting points of the compounds were uncorrected and the purity was checked by tlc. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (DMSO- d_6 ; TMS as internal standard) on a FX 90Q JEOL spectrometer (90 MHz).

Results and Discussion

All the pyrido[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines are yellow coloured, high melting solids and showed ir bands at 3 380–3 340 (NH), 3 120–3 110br (C=NH), 1 195–1 185 strong (C=S) and three bands at 1 585–1 430 cm^{-1} (NH–C=S). The nmr spectra showed the resonance of the NH and C=NH protons in the range δ 7.83–9.08, multiplet at δ 6.50–8.34 due to the aromatic protons, and a singlet at δ 3.82–3.86 due to OCH_3 protons. The CH_2 protons of ethoxy group occurred as a quartet at δ 4.12–4.15 and CH_3 protons as a triplet at δ 1.40–1.44. The ir and nmr spectral data are recorded in Table 2.

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Synthesis of 2-(4'-Nitroanilino)-4-(2'-carbamoylphenoxy)-6-(arylthioureido)-*s*-triazine Derivatives as Antibacterial Agents

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THIOUREA derivatives possess wide therapeutic activities¹. Salicylamide exhibits strong antipyretic, antispasmodic and sedative actions². Moreover salicylamide has marked analgesic property. Phenoxyethers of *s*-triazine are well known fungicides³ and potential therapeutic agents⁴.

Anticipating that the combined presence of N–C=S and 2-carbamoylphenoxy groupings in an *s*-triazine nucleus may enhance antibacterial

activity, we have synthesised 2-(4'-nitroanilino)-4-(2'-carbamoylphenoxy)-6-(arylthioureido)-*s*-triazine derivatives (**1**).

Cyanuric chloride and *p*-nitroaniline in equimolar proportions were condensed. The intermediate so obtained was reacted with salicylamide, followed by reaction with various arylthiourea to get the corresponding *s*-triazine derivatives (**1**).

Experimental

Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected.

2-(4'-Nitroanilino)-4,6-dichloro-*s*-triazine: To a stirred solution of cyanuric chloride (1.84 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone at 0–5°, a solution of *p*-nitroaniline (1.39 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone was added. The reaction mixture was stirred at 0–5° for 2 h maintaining neutral pH. It was then poured into crushed ice, and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from alcohol, (90%), m.p. 290°.

2-(4'-Nitroanilino)-4-(2'-carbamoylphenoxy)-6-chloro-*s*-triazine: To a stirred solution of 2-(4'-nitroanilino)-4,6-dichloro-*s*-triazine (2.86 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone at 35°, was added a solution of salicylamide (1.37 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone over a period of 0.5 h. The temperature was gradually raised to 45° during 2 h with stirring and maintaining a neutral pH. It was then poured onto crushed ice, and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from alcohol, (76%), m.p. 300°.

General method for preparation of 2-(4'-nitroanilino)-4-(2'-carbamoylphenoxy)-6-(arylthioureido)-*s*-triazine (1**)**: A mixture of 2-(4'-nitroanilino)-4-(2'-carbamoylphenoxy)-6-chloro-*s*-triazine (3.87 g, 0.01 mol) and arylthiourea (0.01 mol) in acetone was refluxed for 3 h on a water-bath. It was then treated with crushed ice, and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from alcohol (Table 1): ν_{max} 820–830 (*s*-triazine), 1 265–1 270 (C–O–C), 1 470–1 480 (C–N thiourea), 3 400–3 415 (NH) and 1 615–1 620 cm^{-1} (NHCO).

The compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* at a concentration of 10 mg ml⁻¹ using agar-plate method⁵. Amongst the compounds (Table 1) tested, compound sl. no. 9 showed maximum activity (zone of inhibition 2 and 2.5 mm) and that sl. no. 4 showed minimum activity (zone of inhibition 1.0 and 0.5 mm) against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* respectively.